

BLADDER MOLDING OF DOUBLE LAYERS WALL FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC MATERIAL.

Salomi A^{a,b,c}, Greco A^a, Rametta R^b, Manni O^b, Pacifico T^c, Paladini F^a, Maffezzoli A^a.

a Department of Innovation Engineering – Università di Lecce – via per Monteroni
73100 Lecce, Italy. Tel. tel +390832-297.233 fax +390832.297.525

b Consorzio CETMA - Department of Materials and Structural Engineering – Cittadella
della Ricerca SS Appia km7,300 72100 Brindisi , Italy. Tel. +39.0831.449.111; fax
+39.0831.44.120

c TELCOM SPA Ostuni (Br)

e-mail: andrea.salomi@cetma.it ; andreasalomi@yahoo.it

SUMMARY

In this work, a process for manufacturing double wall component with continuous fiber reinforced polymer was studied. The process is based on bladder molding of thermoplastic matrix composite, within a hollow mould. First a preliminary assessment of bladder molding of commingled woven was performed. Then, a mould and a membrane were properly designed and the molded parts were characterized in terms of physical and mechanical properties, in order to evaluate the effect of processing conditions on the quality of composite. Finally, a double layer wall panel was moulded following the same manufacturing process. It is also under development the production of most complex objects using double layered continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic materials.

Keywords: thermoplastic, commingled, bladder moulding, multi-layer.

INTRODUCTION

In this study a bladder technique for production of double layer part, made of a thermoplastic matrix composite and unreinforced polymer layers was developed. The unreinforced polymer layer and composite layer were coupled by using a bladder moulding process including an heating and cooling stage. The composite layer has structural task and the unreinforced polymeric layer could typically has different kind of purposes such as alimentary contact layer or inner protective layer, outer protective layer, outer esthetical layer or simply to increase the part thickness as well.

Since this study is related to a project (Italian founding grant) on realization of automotive thermoplastic component, the adopted solution in term of layers combination, materials and in term of type of test performed are strictly related to the aims of this project.

In fact potential applications of the process are aesthetically-structural components for lightweight, fuel efficient and environmental friendly vehicles, in order to meet the increasingly stringent environmental European legislation about the reduction of CO₂ emissions, the recycling of end of life vehicles and the new safety standards.

Furthermore the proposed bladder method could also be used to realize an inner protective layer to hollow composite part [1].

Thermoplastic matrix composites, based on commodity polymers, have more and more increasing interest, essentially thanks to their fast processability, high impact and delamination strength, abrasion and chemical resistance, low moisture absorption, unlimited shelf life of raw materials, and low cost. In addition, the ability of thermoplastic matrix composites to be recycled is one of the main advantages over thermosetting [2]. Because of its characteristics of low density, good processability and environmental resistance, isotactic polypropylene (iPP) is considered one of the best thermoplastic candidates for many industrial applications.

During processing of thermoplastic based composites, pressure and temperature are applied to the material to allow fiber impregnation and void fraction reduction. At high temperatures, the low viscosity of the polymer and the applied pressure involve transversal flux of the molten phase, which impregnates the fibers forming a consolidated composite. The flux of the molten material is governed by Darcy's law [3, 4]. As a consequence of this, low viscosities and short migration distance of the polymer matrix enhance the consolidation step, even in presence of low applied pressures. This is usually purchased by using commingled yarn composites, which can be processed at very low pressures.

Processing techniques typically fall into two categories; consolidation between matched dies (matched die forming, hydro forming, rubber block forming and shaped rubber tool forming) and those where the consolidation force is provided by a diaphragm or film (double diaphragm forming, vacuum bag consolidation and autoclave processing) [5].

In this work a bladder technique was adopted because it is the most suitable technology for production of hollow composite component. The bladder technology used in this work was assessed in a previous work [1]. The material preform, which is a commingled yarn of iPP and glass fibers (TWINTEX), is placed inside the mould. A silicone bladder membrane is also placed inside the mould, in order to apply pressure during the thermal cycle and enhance consolidation and fiber impregnation. A layer of unreinforced thermoplastic polymer is added between the silicone and the laminate performs.

In a previous part of the work [1], only the composite material was tested to evaluate the possibility of molding according to the introduced principle. The mould and membrane were properly designed and the molded parts were characterized in terms of physical and mechanical properties, in order to evaluate the effect of processing conditions on the quality of composite.

Once evaluated the best processing conditions for thermoplastic matrix composite with the bladder system the thermoplastic unreinforced thermoplastic polymer layer was added and so double layer was obtained. A subsequent mechanical characterization was performed to evaluate the property of double layered wall material.

It is under development the design of more complex shape part, this for a project mentioned above in which automotive double layer part is the goal.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The material used for composite laminated layer is thermoplastic matrix composite, obtained by laying plies of TWINTEX[®] T PP balanced woven fabric, consisting of yarns of commingled E-glass fibers with iPP (isotactic polypropylene) filaments ($W_{\text{glass}} = 60\%$). TWINTEX plies can be formed into rigid laminates under the contemporary application of heat (up the melt temperature of PP) and pressure. The consolidation behaviour of this material during a non isothermal molding process was also studied in a previous work in terms of thickness versus temperature evolution for an applied constant pressure [1]. In particular different values of pressure were evaluated up to 1 bar and temperature of 215 °C, so the best processing condition were evaluated as those corresponding to maximum mechanical properties and minimum void fraction. Finally, once established the best processing condition for the composite alone, the layer of unreinforced thermoplastic polymer was added during the subsequent molding test.

The unreinforced polymer used as functional layer was LLDPE with a MFI of 3.5 g/10min. For the preliminary test of molding method flat geometries of double layers were moulded with bladder system.

Density evaluation tests on laminated composites were performed by means of a Sartorius GP 3202 balance, equipped with a system for hydrostatic weighting, following the ASTM D 792 standard.

Static mechanical characterization was performed on molded components parallel to the fiber direction in MTS dynamometer equipped with a load cell of 2 KN.

Flexural tests were performed following the ASTM D-790 standard. The support span to thickness ratio was chose at 25:1. Static flexural tests were performed using a strain rate of 0.01 [mm/mm/s], in order to evaluate the flexural stiffness.

The flexural test were conducted by placing the unreinforced polymer layer on the load nose side at first and secondly the composite layer was placed to the load nose side.

The measured stiffness was compared with a theoretical stiffness, calculated from the sample geometry and materials properties. Assuming the conservation of flat sections as in the classical beam theory the following formula was used for calculation of neutral axis position. Scheme used for calculation is reported in Figure 1.

Figure 1- Neutral axis position.

$$z_{AN} = \frac{t_{up}^2 + nt_{TW}^2 + 2nt_{TW}t_{up}}{2(t_{up} + nt_{TW})} \quad (1)$$

Where t_{up} and t_{TW} are respectively the unreinforced thermoplastic polymer and TWNTEX thickness and n is the homogenization coefficient which is the ratio of the composite modulus to the polymer modulus .

the flexural stiffness is easily calculated as the sum of product EI of each material.

$$EI_{calculated} = \sum Ei \cdot Ii \quad (2)$$

Where Ii is the momentum of inertia with respect to the position of the neutral axis, and Ei are the modules of materials.

Once calculated EI is compared with that obtained as output of the flexural test obtained with the formula:

$$EI_{measured} = \frac{K \cdot L^3}{48} \quad (3)$$

Where L is span distance of the test, and K is the experimental stiffness.

Moulding technique description

The process involves lay-up of the commingled preform on the inner surface of the hollow mould. Commingled yarn based preform retains very high flexibility, and can be easily

conformed to meet the shape of the mould. However for characterization purposes flat laminates were provided.

The mould is composed of two halves. The two halves have two flanges, necessary for mold closure. The upper part is provided with a hole, necessary to the bladder extraction and inflation. The hole is closed by means of a plate, which is connected to the pressurization system. The membrane is also sealed in the upper part of the mould ensuring air retaining to permit the related pressurization. To obtain flat panel the material was placed only on the rectangular bottom surface of the mold. A symmetrical 0/90 stacking sequence was adopted for composite layers. In addition a last layer of polymer sheet, 1.5 mm in thickness, were placed on the top of sequence.

Consolidation of the composite is obtained by contemporary effect of pressure and temperature. In order to apply pressure during heating and cooling stage, a pressurized silicone membrane is acting on the inner surface of the material. The mould with the mentioned materials and the membrane are placed inside a convection oven, where the matrix of the composite and polymer sheet melt.

Heating of the material takes place by conduction from the mould surface. During consolidation, when the PP matrix melts, the air which is removed by the composite can escape through the mould parting zone. After reaching the complete compaction of the composite laminate the mould is extracted from the oven and cooling phase takes place. The pressure is applied not only through the whole heating process, but during the cooling stage too, in order to reduce warpage due to solidification of the polymer matrix.

A scheme of the mould system with the lay-up of the commingled perform, unreinforced polymer and membrane is shown in Figure 2. Also a silicone frame was used to prevent lateral squeezing during the molding of flat panels. In figure 2 is reported the molded double layer panel.

Figure 2- Mould system scheme.

Figure 3- Double layer moulded part.

The mould used in this work is an aluminium mould, which ensures better heat transfer and lower weight than steel. The mould has a very simple shape, a box (25x 25 x 20 cm) with inner corners radius of 3cm between the walls. In mould design, two factors have been taken into account: mechanical resistance during pressurization, and heat transfer through mould thickness. Although increasing mould thickness can improve mechanical resistance, it also involves longer cycle times.

Moreover, in order to ensure planarity of composite surface, the deformation of the mould plane surfaces must be limited.

In order to reduce cycle times, the thickness of the mould was taken as the minimum determined from resistance and displacement equations, i.e. 13mm.

The membrane was a silicone membrane which is able to withstand high stresses at high temperatures. Its size and shape were designed as to meet the cavity of the mold.

Thermal cycle

Consolidation of the composite takes place as an effect of melting of the polymer matrix. Also, during the cooling stage the crystallization conditions of the polymer matrix are determined by the

cooling rate. Consequently, knowledge of the thermal effects arising during the process is very important in order to understand and optimise the process itself. The temperatures during processing were measured by means of thermocouples placed at different positions on the mould.

Figure 4- Adopted thermal cycle.

As it can be observed, the temperature increases during heating stage. The temperature at the TW-mold interface is higher than other temperatures, and the difference between TW-mold interface and TW-U.T.P. interface (Unreinforced Thermoplastic Polymer interface) is related to the low thermal conductivity of polymer composite, and to the thickness of six layers of composite preform. The temperature of the U.T.P.-Bladder interface is the lower one, since the membrane and air inside of it also acts as a thermal insulator. The temperature gradient through composite thickness decreases when the polymer matrix melts. This is attributed to the compaction of the composite, which involves an increase of its thermal conductivity, and a decrease of its thickness. Also the melting and crystallization stage of LLDPE can be observed monitoring the U.T.P.-Bladder interface temperature. The temperature of the system increases up to a maximum value, and the mold is extracted from the oven. The choice of the maximum temperature is very important in definition of the process times and product quality[1]. During the cooling stage, taking place in quiescent air, the temperature gradients are very low. The material can be extracted from the mold after the temperature becomes lower than a critical value, which mainly depends from crystallization conditions, and cooling rates.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Characterization of molded samples

The best processing condition were chosen as those corresponding to maximum density of the composite laminate.

In the figure 5, the result of density measurement for different processing conditions for 6 layers of composite are reported. In particular six layer of composite were formed at four different processing conditions which are 215°C as maximum temperature measured at the interface rubber-composite and respectively 0.1 bar, 0.3 bar, 0.5 bar and 1 bar of applied pressure.

Figure 5 – Density variation under different processing pressures for temperature peak of 215°C.

Results show density improvement with increasing pressure, which is due to voids reduction under increasing of moulding pressure.

Also the flexural strength and modulus of the composite were evaluated for the same processing conditions listed above and were also compared with those reported in the technical data sheet of material.

Figure 6 – Flexural modulus of TWINTEX under different processing pressures for temperature peak of 215°C.

Figure 7 - Flexural strength of TWINTEX under different processing pressures for temperature peak of 215°C.

As it can be observed in figure 6 and figure 7 also flexural strength and modulus increase with increasing processing pressure.

As it can be observed, the flexural strength of the laminates obtained are higher than those reported as reference value of the technical data sheet. The elastic modulus is lightly lower but also comparable with that reported in the technical data sheet of Twintex.

As evidenced from results reported above the best processing conditions for composite are $T=215^{\circ}\text{C}$ as peak processing temperature and $p=1$ bar as pressure applied by the bladder.

Once established the processing conditions which gave the best quality of composite in terms of higher density, and higher mechanical performance the layer of polymer was added in the staking sequence and then double layer was obtained.

Figure 8 - Flexural test on double layer.

In the figure 9 the stress strain curves obtained from flexural tests by placing the polymer layer on the intrados and extrados are reported.

Figure 9 – Flexural test output on double.

The comparison of theoretical and measured flexural stiffness are reported in the following table 1. A good correspondence of calculated and measured flexural stiffness value is evidenced.

Table 1 – Results of flexural test on double layer.

N	Section configuration	Maximum Force [N]	Maximum displacement [mm]	Stiffness [N/mm]	K	Measured [kNmm ²]	EI	Calculated [kNmm ²]	EI
1	TWINTeX on the extrados	216.8±13.7	13.7±1.3	19.5±0.2		602.8±15.7		605.7±15.8	
2	TWINTeX on the intrados	249.2±17	16.1±1.9	18.7±0.2		578±5.8		555.4±21.7	

In addition, as expected the configuration 2 exhibits maximum stress and corresponding displacement higher than configuration 1, as reported in table 1. In fact, with this configuration, the maximum stress is expected on TWINTeX side and it is smaller if compared with that of TWINTeX when it is placed on the extrados side i.e. as configuration 1, due to curvature of the specimen during the flexural test.

Furthermore, in both configurations, the samples broke within the twintex and not by shearing and debonding of the two layers, indicating an adequate adhesion between the composite and the LLDPE layer.

CONCLUSION

In this work, a process for manufacturing double wall component with continuous fiber reinforced polymer was studied. The process is based on bladder molding of thermoplastic matrix composite, where the mould part is a female one.

First the best processing condition for composite layer was set, secondly a double layers wall material prototype was manufactured.

Since then the properties of each single layer are well known, the properties of the section in term of flexural stiffness was measured with flexural test and compared with calculated flexural stiffness. A good correspondence of calculated and measured value is evidenced in table 1.

This mean that each layer exhibits the expected properties and then this confirm the quality of the process. Also an adequate adhesion between the composite and the LLDPE layer was observed.

Other kind of double layer materials are still under study and will be soon issued. Also a method to compare different interfacial strength will be proposed.

The potential applications of the process are components for lightweight, fuel efficient and environmental friendly vehicles. This is the aim of a Italian grant in which the authors are working in collaboration with CRF (research centre of FIAT).

REFERENCES

-
- 1 Salomi A, Greco A, Felling F, Manni O, Maffezzoli A, *Adv. Pol. Techn.* Vol 26 N. 1 pp. 21-32, (2007).
 - 2 Pegoretti, A. Ricco, T. *J. Mater. Sci.*, 36, 4637–4641, (2001)
 - 3 Phillips, R., Devrim, A., Manson, J.A.E. *Compos. Part A* 29A, 395-402, (1998)
 - 4 Michaud, V. J. Manson, J.A.E. *J. Compos. Mater.* 35, 1150-1173, (2001)
 - 5 Wakeman, M.D. Cain, T.A. Rudd, C.D. Brooks, R. Long, A.C. *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 58, 1879-1898, (1998)